

K-Means Clustering in Machine Learning – a Review

Manu Mitra*

Department of Alumnus with
Electrical Engineering, University of
Bridgeport, Bridgeport, CT, United
States

*Corresponding author:

Manu Mitra, Department of Alumnus
with Electrical Engineering,
University of Bridgeport, Bridgeport,
CT, United States

Received: July 14, 2019

Published: September 4, 2019

Volume: 01; **Issue:** 04

To Cite This Article:

Manu Mitra. K-Means Clustering
in Machine Learning – a Review.
Peer Res Nest. 2019 - 1(4)
PNEST.19.09.004.

This work is licensed under Creative
Commons Attribution 4.0 License

Follow us in social sites:

Abstract

K means clustering is unsupervised machine learning algorithm. It aims to partition n observations into k clusters where each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean, serving as a prototype of the cluster. This results in a partitioning of the data space into Voronoi cells.

In this review paper a sample data from UCI is taken and K-means algorithm is applied on Iris data set. Multi class logistic regression is also performed to compare its performance.

Trained resultant model graph for K-means clustering is plotted.

Score Model graphs such as F1 log scale, frequency log scale, cumulative distribution, probability density of multiclass logistic regression for "Iris-setosa" are plotted to view its performance

Score Model graphs F1 log scale, frequency log scale, cumulative distribution, and probability density of multiclass logistic regression for "Iris-versicolor" are plotted to view its performance Figure 1.

Figure 1: Illustrates logo for the experiment used for K-means clustering. Image Credit: Azure AI for Microsoft [2].

Keywords: K-Means Clustering; Machine Learning; Data Sets

Introduction

A cluster is a collection of data points collected together because of certain similarities. Target number is defined which refers to the number of centroids required in the dataset. A centroid can be an imaginary or real location representing the centre of the cluster.

To process learning data, the K-means algorithm starts with a first group of randomly selected centroids which are used as beginning points for every cluster, and then it performs iterative calculations to optimize the positions of the centroids [1]

Literature Review

This method demonstrates clustering using K-means algorithm using UCI Iris data set. There is also multi class regression to implement multi-class classification and understand its performance with K-means clustering.

In the data processing section, Reader module is used to read the data directly from UCI. Another module is also used to clean missing data to remove any empty row from the data set.

In the next module metadata editor is used to change the column names since column names are not defined in this particular case. Then split module is used to divide the whole data set ran-

domly into training and test data set, setting the fraction of rows in training set.

In this model K-means clustering is used and compared with the model created by using Multiclass logistic regression module [3].

K-means clustering experiment

A simulation for K-means clustering was performed with the below data

Representation of K-means clustering experiment

Figure 2

Figure 2: Illustrates flow representation of Group of Iris Data utilizing K-mean clustering and multiclass logistic regression [1].

Raw data for K-mean clustering from UCI

Figure 3: Illustrates Column 1 data histogram.

Figure 4: Illustrates Column 1 data histogram.

Table 1: UCI Raw data for K-means clustering.

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5
5.1	3.5	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.9	3	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.7	3.2	1.3	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.6	3.1	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3.6	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.4	3.9	1.7	0.4	Iris-setosa
4.6	3.4	1.4	0.3	Iris-setosa
5	3.4	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.4	2.9	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.9	3.1	1.5	0.1	Iris-setosa
5.4	3.7	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.8	3.4	1.6	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.8	3	1.4	0.1	Iris-setosa
4.3	3	1.1	0.1	Iris-setosa
5.8	4	1.2	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.7	4.4	1.5	0.4	Iris-setosa
5.4	3.9	1.3	0.4	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.5	1.4	0.3	Iris-setosa
5.7	3.8	1.7	0.3	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.8	1.5	0.3	Iris-setosa
5.4	3.4	1.7	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.7	1.5	0.4	Iris-setosa
4.6	3.6	1	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.3	1.7	0.5	Iris-setosa
4.8	3.4	1.9	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3	1.6	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3.4	1.6	0.4	Iris-setosa
5.2	3.5	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.2	3.4	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.7	3.2	1.6	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.8	3.1	1.6	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.4	3.4	1.5	0.4	Iris-setosa
5.2	4.1	1.5	0.1	Iris-setosa
5.5	4.2	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.9	3.1	1.5	0.1	Iris-setosa
5	3.2	1.2	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.5	3.5	1.3	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.9	3.1	1.5	0.1	Iris-setosa
4.4	3	1.3	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.4	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3.5	1.3	0.3	Iris-setosa
4.5	2.3	1.3	0.3	Iris-setosa
4.4	3.2	1.3	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3.5	1.6	0.6	Iris-setosa
5.1	3.8	1.9	0.4	Iris-setosa
4.8	3	1.4	0.3	Iris-setosa

5.1	3.8	1.6	0.2	Iris-setosa
4.6	3.2	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
5.3	3.7	1.5	0.2	Iris-setosa
5	3.3	1.4	0.2	Iris-setosa
7	3.2	4.7	1.4	Iris-versicolor
6.4	3.2	4.5	1.5	Iris-versicolor
6.9	3.1	4.9	1.5	Iris-versicolor
5.5	2.3	4	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.5	2.8	4.6	1.5	Iris-versicolor
5.7	2.8	4.5	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.3	3.3	4.7	1.6	Iris-versicolor
4.9	2.4	3.3	1	Iris-versicolor
6.6	2.9	4.6	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.2	2.7	3.9	1.4	Iris-versicolor
5	2	3.5	1	Iris-versicolor
5.9	3	4.2	1.5	Iris-versicolor
6	2.2	4	1	Iris-versicolor
6.1	2.9	4.7	1.4	Iris-versicolor
5.6	2.9	3.6	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.7	3.1	4.4	1.4	Iris-versicolor
5.6	3	4.5	1.5	Iris-versicolor
5.8	2.7	4.1	1	Iris-versicolor
6.2	2.2	4.5	1.5	Iris-versicolor
5.6	2.5	3.9	1.1	Iris-versicolor
5.9	3.2	4.8	1.8	Iris-versicolor
6.1	2.8	4	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.3	2.5	4.9	1.5	Iris-versicolor
6.1	2.8	4.7	1.2	Iris-versicolor
6.4	2.9	4.3	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.6	3	4.4	1.4	Iris-versicolor
6.8	2.8	4.8	1.4	Iris-versicolor
6.7	3	5	1.7	Iris-versicolor
6	2.9	4.5	1.5	Iris-versicolor
5.7	2.6	3.5	1	Iris-versicolor
5.5	2.4	3.8	1.1	Iris-versicolor
5.5	2.4	3.7	1	Iris-versicolor
5.8	2.7	3.9	1.2	Iris-versicolor
6	2.7	5.1	1.6	Iris-versicolor
5.4	3	4.5	1.5	Iris-versicolor
6	3.4	4.5	1.6	Iris-versicolor
6.7	3.1	4.7	1.5	Iris-versicolor
6.3	2.3	4.4	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.6	3	4.1	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.5	2.5	4	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.5	2.6	4.4	1.2	Iris-versicolor
6.1	3	4.6	1.4	Iris-versicolor
5.8	2.6	4	1.2	Iris-versicolor
5	2.3	3.3	1	Iris-versicolor

5.6	2.7	4.2	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.7	3	4.2	1.2	Iris-versicolor
5.7	2.9	4.2	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.2	2.9	4.3	1.3	Iris-versicolor
5.1	2.5	3	1.1	Iris-versicolor
5.7	2.8	4.1	1.3	Iris-versicolor
6.3	3.3	6	2.5	Iris-virginica
5.8	2.7	5.1	1.9	Iris-virginica
7.1	3	5.9	2.1	Iris-virginica
6.3	2.9	5.6	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.5	3	5.8	2.2	Iris-virginica
7.6	3	6.6	2.1	Iris-virginica
4.9	2.5	4.5	1.7	Iris-virginica
7.3	2.9	6.3	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.7	2.5	5.8	1.8	Iris-virginica
7.2	3.6	6.1	2.5	Iris-virginica
6.5	3.2	5.1	2	Iris-virginica
6.4	2.7	5.3	1.9	Iris-virginica
6.8	3	5.5	2.1	Iris-virginica
5.7	2.5	5	2	Iris-virginica
5.8	2.8	5.1	2.4	Iris-virginica
6.4	3.2	5.3	2.3	Iris-virginica
6.5	3	5.5	1.8	Iris-virginica
7.7	3.8	6.7	2.2	Iris-virginica
7.7	2.6	6.9	2.3	Iris-virginica
6	2.2	5	1.5	Iris-virginica
6.9	3.2	5.7	2.3	Iris-virginica
5.6	2.8	4.9	2	Iris-virginica
7.7	2.8	6.7	2	Iris-virginica
6.3	2.7	4.9	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.7	3.3	5.7	2.1	Iris-virginica
7.2	3.2	6	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.2	2.8	4.8	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.1	3	4.9	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.4	2.8	5.6	2.1	Iris-virginica
7.2	3	5.8	1.6	Iris-virginica
7.4	2.8	6.1	1.9	Iris-virginica
7.9	3.8	6.4	2	Iris-virginica
6.4	2.8	5.6	2.2	Iris-virginica
6.3	2.8	5.1	1.5	Iris-virginica
6.1	2.6	5.6	1.4	Iris-virginica
7.7	3	6.1	2.3	Iris-virginica
6.3	3.4	5.6	2.4	Iris-virginica
6.4	3.1	5.5	1.8	Iris-virginica
6	3	4.8	1.8	Iris-virginica
6.9	3.1	5.4	2.1	Iris-virginica
6.7	3.1	5.6	2.4	Iris-virginica
6.9	3.1	5.1	2.3	Iris-virginica

5.8	2.7	5.1	1.9	Iris-virginica
6.8	3.2	5.9	2.3	Iris-virginica
6.7	3.3	5.7	2.5	Iris-virginica
6.7	3	5.2	2.3	Iris-virginica
6.3	2.5	5	1.9	Iris-virginica
6.5	3	5.2	2	Iris-virginica
6.2	3.4	5.4	2.3	Iris-virginica
5.9	3	5.1	1.8	Iris-virginica

Figure 5: Illustrates Column 3 data histogram.

Figure 6: Illustrates Column 4 data histogram.

Figure 7: Illustrates Column 5 data histogram.

Table 2: column 1 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	3.054
2	Median	3
3	Min	2
4	Max	4.4
5	Standard Deviation	0.4336
6	Unique Values	23
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 3: Column 2 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	3.054
2	Median	3
3	Min	2
4	Max	4.4
5	Standard Deviation	0.4336
6	Unique Values	23
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 4: Column 3 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	3.7587
2	Median	4.35
3	Min	1
4	Max	6.9
5	Standard Deviation	1.7644
6	Unique Values	43
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 5: Column 3 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	1.1987
2	Median	1.3
3	Min	0.1
4	Max	2.5
5	Standard Deviation	0.7632
6	Unique Values	22
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 6: Column 5 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Unique Values	3
2	Missing Values	0
3	Feature Type	String Feature

Table 1, Figure 3, Table 2, Figure 4, Table 3, Figure 5, Table 4, Figure 6, Table 5, Figure 7 Table 6

Results of experiments

Results of after training a model using K-means algorithm

Figure 8: Illustrates trained resultant model for K-means clustering.

Figure 8

Score Model Results of each column graphs and values after training a model using Multiclass Logistic Regression

Evaluate Model Results of each column graphs and values after training a model using Multiclass Logistic Regression

Figure 9, Table 7, Figure 10, Table 8, Figure 11, Table 9, Figure 12, Table 10, Figure 13, Table 11, Figure 14-23

Figure 24, Table 12

Table 7: Resultant column 1 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	5.8083
2	Median	5.7
3	Min	4.4
4	Max	7.9
5	Standard Deviation	0.8546
6	Unique Values	30
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 8: Resultant column 2 statistics.

SI No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	3.135
2	Median	3.1
3	Min	2.2
4	Max	4.4
5	Standard Deviation	0.425
6	Unique Values	18
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Table 9: Resultant column 3 statistics.

Sl No	Statistics	Value
1	Mean	3.5333
2	Median	4
3	Min	1.3
4	Max	6.7
5	Standard Deviation	1.8566
6	Unique Values	29
7	Missing Values	0
8	Feature Type	Numeric Feature

Figure 11: Illustrates Resultant Column 3 frequency log scale for Score Model of multiclass logistic regression.

Figure 12: Illustrates Resultant Column 4 cumulative distribution for Score Model of multiclass logistic regression.

Figure 13: Illustrates Resultant Column 5 (Label) probability density for Score Model of multiclass logistic regression.

Figure 14: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-setosa".

Figure 15: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-setosa" log scale.

Figure 16: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-setosa" frequency log scale.

Figure 17: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-setosa" cumulative distribution.

Figure 18: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-setosa" probability density.

Figure 19: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-versicolor".

Figure 20: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-versicolor" log scale.

Figure 21: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-versicolor" frequency log scale.

Figure 22: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-versicolor" cumulative distribution.

Figure 23: Illustrates histogram of Scored Probabilities for Class "Iris-versicolor" probability density.

Figure 24: Illustrates Confusion Matrix.

Results

What is claimed in this review article are

1. Histogram of column 1, column 2, column 3 and column 3 of data is plotted after cleaning of data.
2. Statistics of the graphs are noted
3. Trained resultant model for K-mean clustering is plotted
4. Score Model for F1 log scale, frequency log scale, cumulative distribution, probability density of multiclass logistic regression for "Iris-setosa" are plotted
5. Score Model for F1 log scale, frequency log scale, cumulative distribution, probability density of multiclass logistic regression for "Iris-versicolor" are plotted

Conclusion

In this review article all the values are taken as default values which are documented in Tables. Results, graph, accuracy etc., vary for the change in the parameters and its values.

Author also want to take note: there is change of the graph's statistics for overall accuracy, average accuracy, micro-averaged precision, macro-averaged precision, micro-averaged recall and macro-averaged recall after training the module for multiclass logistic regression.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest as per Author's point of view.

References

1. Michael J Garbade (2018) Understanding K-means Clustering in Machine Learning.
2. Azure AI (2015) Clustering: Group iris data.
3. Microsoft (2016) Microsoft Azure Machine Learning Studio.